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Poster

Abiotic, biotic and cultural resources on the aspiring UNESCO Global Geopark Valleys of Cantabria

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Valleys of Cantabria aspiring Geopark covers approximately 600 km² in the north of Spain; it is characterized by steep slopes, with heights ranging from 0 to 1600 m.a.s.l. The territory includes 19 municipalities (some of them with serious problems of depopulation) with a population of 60,604 inhabitants. The main economic activity in the territory is the tertiary sector (mainly tourism), which is predominant in the coastal and urban areas; live-stock farming plays a major role in rural environments, and fishing, linked to the canning industry. The Geopark candidate includes sites of high geological interest developed on Mesozoic materials affected by tectonic processes, which have been modelled by different agents that have acted in the area throughout the Quaternary, giving rise to glacial, karstic, fluvial and coastal morphologies. The different elements presented are excellent examples of the evolution suffered by the relief, allowing the different evolutionary stages of coastal areas (Atlantic Ocean) to be linked to the rivers Asón and Miera. In this sense, the main interest to visit the aspiring Geopark is the excellent representation and diversity of geomorphological environments, processes and geomorphological forms that can be observed from the head of the valleys to the coastline. The high ecological value of the existing natural heritage in the proposed Geopark is highlighted by the presence of some of the most biologically diverse places in Spain: a Ramsar zone, a Natural Park, five Special Areas of Conservation, Natura 2000 European Ecological Network, a Special Protection Area for Birds and three areas catalogued as Important Bird Areas and Biodiversity. The applicant Geopark has an important cultural heritage; the Covalanas cave, declared a World Heritage Site in 2008, three cultural itineraries of the Council of Europe are present in the territory, and a large number of prehistoric sites, megalithic constructions, religious, architectural and industrial buildings which are important examples of the culture in this area. In the future Geopark exist local producers on agriculture or organic farming, livestock or fishing. Thus, there is a high quality of agricultural and fishing products and the agro-food industries which fix the population in the rural environment, while at the same time preserving local traditions and villages. Also, the active tourism companies offer geotourism interpreted activities in contact with nature and the geology of the surroundings: trekking, climbing, canoeing, caving, bird watching, via ferrata or cycling activities. The roads and paths that run through the territory are suitable for all audiences. The declaration of this area as a Global Geopark is a great opportunity to disseminate geology and geomorphology, as well as other activities linked to human activities, in addition to becoming a geology and nature classroom for the educational schools and colleges distributed in the territory.

Keywords: Aspiring Geopark Valleys of Cantabria-Spain, Geological heritage, Natural heritage, Cultural heritage, Geotourism activities

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Bonachea et al., (2019). Proposal for a declaration of a geopark in the Valleys of Soba, Asón and Miera (Cantabria, Spain). Regional Conference on Geomorphology, International Association of Geomorphologists. 19-21 Septiembre 2019, Atenas, Grecia. Bonachea et al., (2021). Geological heritage in the Valleys of Cantabria Geopark project. X International Online ProGEO Symposium, Spain, 7-10th June, 2021.

Abiotic, biotic and cultural resources in the aspiring UNESCO Geopark Valleys of Cantabria

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INTRODUCTION

The aspiring Geopark Valleys of Cantabria is located between the geographical coordinates 43° 9' 50" N-43° 30' 5" N and 3° 20' 00" W-3° 40' 55" W. The applicant Geopark is located in the eastern area of Cantabria, in the north of Spain (**FIG. 1**), bordering the provinces of Burgos (Castilla-León) and Vizcaya (Basque Country). It includes all or part of the basins corresponding to the valleys of the rivers Miera and Asón.

The territory covers approximately 600 km² and includes 19 municipalities (some of them with serious problems of depopulation) with a population of 60,600 inhabitants. The relief is characterized by steep slopes, with heights ranging from 0 to 1600 m.a.s.l. The main economic activity in the territory is the tertiary sector (mainly tourism), which is predominant in the coastal and urban areas; live-stock farming plays a major role in rural environments, and fishing, linked to the canning industry.

GEOLOGICAL AND GEOMORPHOLOGICAL RESOURCES

The Geopark candidate includes 66 sites of high geological interest developed on Mesozoic materials (**FIG. 2**) affected by tectonic processes, which have been modelled by different agents that have acted in the area throughout the Quaternary, giving rise to glacial, karstic, fluvial and coastal morphologies. The different elements presented are excellent examples of the evolution suffered by the relief, allowing the different evolutionary stages of coastal areas (Atlantic Ocean) to be linked to the rivers Asón and Miera. In this sense, the main interest to visit the aspiring Geopark is the excellent representation and diversity of geomorphological environments, processes and geomorphological forms that can be observed from the head of the valleys to the coastline (**FIG. 3**). These sites are very good examples to show geomorphological processes to the society.

BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES

The high ecological value of the existing natural heritage in the proposed Geopark is highlighted by the presence of some of the most biologically diverse places in Spain: a Ramsar zone, a Natural Park, five Special Areas of Conservation, Natura 2000 European Ecological Network, a Special Protection Area for Birds and three areas catalogued as Important Bird Areas and Biodiversity (**FIG. 4**).

CULTURAL RESOURCES

The applicant Geopark has an important cultural heritage; the Covalanas cave, declared a World Heritage Site in 2008, three cultural itineraries of the Council of Europe are present in the territory, and a large number of prehistoric sites, megalithic constructions, religious, architectural and industrial buildings which are important examples of the culture in this area (**FIG. 5**).

GEOTOURISM ACTIVITIES

In the future Geopark exist local producers on agriculture or organic farming, livestock or fishing. Thus, there is a high quality of agricultural and fishing products and the agro-food industries which fix the population in the rural environment, while at the same time preserving local traditions and villages. Also, the active tourism companies offer geotourism interpreted activities in contact with nature and the geology of the surroundings: trekking, climbing, canoeing, caving, bird watching, via ferrata or cycling activities. The roads and paths that run through the territory are suitable for all audiences. The declaration of this area as a Global Geopark is a great opportunity to disseminate geology and geomorphology, as well as other activities linked to human activities, in addition to becoming a geology and nature classroom for the educational schools and colleges distributed in the territory.

CONCLUSIONS

Since 2017, the Valleys of Cantabria Geopark project has been cooperating with other Geoparks, within the framework of the European ATLANTIC GEOPARKS project (Transnational Interreg Atlantic Area Cooperation Program). The participation in different forums, conferences, courses and work meetings has been an important experience and has contributed to improving the quality of the proposal presented here to make this territory part of the Global Geoparks Network.

The main contribution it makes is the excellent representation and diversity of environments, processes and geomorphological forms which allow to explain the functioning and modelling affecting the Earth system. Up to 66 Geosites have been identified, and this inventory still continues, among which are: glacial morphologies, karstic processes, coastal-type forms and wind modelling processes, fluvial environment, paleontological sites, of great interest for the study of the climate during the Holocene and to determine the position of the coastline in these moments. In addition, of this enormous geomorphological diversity, there are other elements of interest as: structural and tectonic, mineral, stratigraphic or hydrogeological.